

Relationship between Rumination and Stress among Men and Women

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Abstract

This study focuses on the relationship between rumination and stress among people of age groups 18-45 years (Ist age group (18-30 years) and IInd age group (31-45 years). The association between ruminating and its associated factors has been the subject of extensive research. But still, research is scarce on rumination. The study examine the relationship between rumination and stress among people of the 18-45 age groups separately and compared their results. Rumination has been different in men and women but specifically, the correlation was stronger for women than men. A separate survey for middle-aged people (31-45 age group) was conducted. The findings confirm many of the hypotheses about the connection between stress and rumination in both men and women. A strong rumination relationship with stress among women is mostly associated with lower resilience levels and diminished self-concept in comparison to men

Key Words: Rumination, stress, resilience, self- concept

"Stress is like the tension on a stringed violin." There should be enough strain to generate music, but not so much that it snaps." "Stress is a condition or experience that happens when an individual considers that demands beat the individual's ability to activate own and communal resources. It is brought on by too much work, unrealistic expectations, and unusual circumstances. It has the potential to make you physically and emotionally ill.

It may provide the necessary vigor to deal with competitors.

Nobody is stress-free; it is an unavoidable aspect of life.

Gain a deeper comprehension of life, one must enjoy one's existence.

It encourages you to perform at a higher level.

On a chronological basis, chronic stress is the most damaging sort of stress. It wears a person down to the point of irreversible loss. A person who is suffering from chronic stress will constantly appear depressed. Chronic stress is always the result of episodic acute stress. Chronic stress is the result of emotional tension over an extended period over which a person feels powerless. Chronic stress can develop because of daily pressures that are neglected or inadequately managed, as well as traumatic occurrences. Chronic stress has major implications, especially when it adds to anxiety and depression. In most circumstances, stress has several effects on a person. When he is under duress, he has a different appearance. "Stress is something that takes the light from your face," a specialist in the IT area correctly stated. It's been called a thief of slumber and joy by some. Many people have differing viewpoints on the impact and emotions it has on an individual. We can count the following as common reflections for a better comprehension of it:

Stress takes away light Your Face

As the level of stress increases, a person becomes dull. He begins to ignore his routine in favour of pondering its origins and potential solutions to the problems that have arisen. Variations in the routine can principal to well-being difficulties such as increased or decreased appetite, sleeplessness, depression, and so on. People who are close to you may not notice the change in your

health and appearance, but others who visit you after a long time will notice the change immediately.

It does not let you Sleep Properly

A person who is stressed will never be able to get a good night's sleep. Stressed people frequently start taking medication for it, whether deliberately or unknowingly. They initially complain of headaches, colds and flu, throat infections, stomach problems, and other ailments. All these illnesses have alcohol in them, which makes people drowsy. It may begin with a simple physician's prescription for paracetamol, levocetirizine, avail, or other pain relievers, but it eventually leads to the worried person being prescribed sleeping drugs daily.

It may drive you in Gloomy Mood

The most prevalent symptom of someone who is stressed is that he or she appears sad. People who are suffering from uncontrollable tension will appear to be bearing the world's sorrows on their shoulders. It makes people depressed. They are unable to appreciate life.

Stress Enhances Negativity

When confronted with a stressful scenario, a person becomes more inventive. An individual who is subjected to its effects will be compelled to think adversely. He can make a big deal out of nothing or cause a ruckus for no reason. They'll come up with some strange notions out of nowhere that no one is willing to believe.

Company of the stressed may cause stress.

It is the company that makes a difference. It is well-known in Panchatantra stories that a man is known by the company he maintains. As a result, it's no surprise that being in the company of a stressed person makes you feel stressed. Then one could wonder why a joyful person can't make a worried person happy. The solution is straightforward: negative information spreads quickly, whereas positive information takes longer to propagate. For your own mental health's sake, it's best to avoid being in the company of a stressed individual.

Stress puts you in isolation.

Anxious people are more likely to be critical of everything. They get anxious to the point where they

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criticize everyone. They are willing to put their relationship on the line if it means avoiding full isolation.

Stress keeps you Busy Whole Day but the Output Seems to be Nil.

In Bhojpuri, there is a proverb that says, "Sab Din Chale, Adhaie Kosh," which means, "I toiled all day but got nothing." This adage is ideal for someone who is stressed. He or she may appear to be busy all day, but the production will be tiny. There could be a number of reasons for this, but the most common is the presence of stress.

Other People will find Stressed before you take Notice of It

It is fairly easy to spot a stressed person based on his or her look, demeanour, interactions, attitude, and other factors. Anxiety, worry, restless behaviour, a dull face, and other psychosomatic symptoms are all plainly visible in a stressed individual. The worried person, on the other hand, is completely unconscious of these changes. As a result, family members and friends have a moral obligation to recognise such changes in their loved ones and offer assistance in rescuing them as soon as possible.

Stress, sometimes, may be Fatal to Person of Weak Willpower

There's a potential that a person will develop suicidal tendencies in stressful circumstances. It could be fatal for people with a weak willpower. You never know when a normal tension would turn into a phobia or schizophrenia. In all age categories, male suicide deaths are higher than female suicide deaths. There are 14 thousand reasons why people commit suicide, but they are all linked to stress. As a result, it is critical to comprehend this component of stress. Teenagers make the most unsuccessful suicide attempts, according to several research.

Loss of Interest and Charm in Life

Stress is a detriment to your ability to enjoy life. You want something, and you won't be happy until you get it. Make a decision to either give it up or achieve it. The inability to achieve your goal will because you worry and leave you stuck in a depressed and gloomy mind-set. As a result, you will begin to lose interest and charm in life. One of the most noticeable characteristics of stress is that it causes you to withdraw from your usual life, including your family, friends, and hobbies.

Loss of appetite

Stress and appetite are inextricably linked. Depending on the type of stress a person is experiencing, their hunger will follow a pattern. Someone who is stressed may have a higher appetite, while someone who is not stressed may have a lower appetite. However, appetite is likely to decrease in the majority of patients.

Emotional Instability

Unmanageable stress in one's life causes emotional distress. He might want to lock himself in a room, or he might not want to talk to anyone, or he might not want to listen to what they have to say. When stress

spirals out of control, it becomes even worse. Even little irritations irritate the person. Someone's behaviour can quickly drive a stressed individual insane. Another trait of stressed people who are experiencing emotional turmoil is forgetfulness. They may experience a total emotional breakdown.

Rumination

Rumination is an unhealthy way to deal with stress that involves obsessively focusing on the causes, effects, and interpretations of one's depression symptoms rather than actively trying to find a way to change the situation that is causing the symptoms (Nolen Hoeksema, 1991). Rumination is characterized by thoughts that are passive and repetitive rather than only by their content. Rumination was defined by Kuhl (1981) as analytical thought on the origins and 26 effects of an internal state (such as mood) and an external state (such as difficulties) that have evolved into an aim in and of themselves rather than a strategy for taking productive action. Therefore, the term "rumination" can be used to describe any kind of thinking that has a propensity to repeat itself. When there are no pressing external pressures, a type of conscious thought centered on recurrent instrument designs is known as rumination. Rumination can be defined as a series of extended, self-centered, negative, and repeating thoughts that arise mostly as a reaction to initial unpleasant ideas. The phrase Empirical evidence suggests that rumination contributes to the development and upkeep of anxiety and depression. Theory accounts with empirical evidence suggest that rumination is brought on by unfulfilled aspirations. Rumination is thought to be more prevalent in palliative patients and their caregivers because living with a life-limiting illness can make objectives for the future and present unachievable or necessitate reevaluation.

Rumination types one is Brooding and the second is Reflection. Brooding is depicted as focused thinking on abstract, random obstacles, and sundry passive thoughts. It has been defined as having passive judgmental thoughts about one's mood. It is associated with problem solving. An individual with a ruminating thought focus is inclined to think more about the problem as also the consequences of the problem that he may have to face soon (ii) Self-reflection is described by more common self-reflection trends like writing down and analyzing emotion in an attempt at problem-solving. It has been defined as a conscious inward focus intended to gain insights into depressive symptoms being experienced by the individual. According to Trapnell and Campbell (1999), rumination is a disturbed kind of self-attentive concentration characterized by recurrent feelings of rage, despair, and anxiety as well as thoughts about imagined distortions, risks, and injustices to the self. Response styles model (Nolen-Hoeksema, year 1991) states that, about depressive rumination, people who think about their depressive symptoms—repeatedly and passively thinking about the reasons for them,

effects, and implications—experience more severe and prolonged depressive moods than people who do not ruminate. It has been demonstrated that depressive rumination obstructs problem-solving, instrumental behavior, optimistic thinking, and relational interactions. In addition to depression, it is linked to other types of psychopathologies such as worry, overdoing, drug abuse, and self-destruction (Nolen Hoeksema, Wisco, & Lyubomirsky, 2008). When they ruminate, those who are anxious or clinically depressed seem to reflect extra negatively about the present, the future, and the past. Ruminating dysphoric participants instinctively access more bad memories from their recent pasts and report unfavorable occurrences that have occurred more frequently throughout their lives than dysphoric individuals who are encouraged to divert from negative ideas. Dysphoric individuals are forced to detour from bad thoughts, and they naturally talk about difficult issues like family strife or financial difficulties, whereas non-dysphoric contributors typically discuss happier circumstances they are facing.

Resilience

George A. Bonino (2002) The capability for adults through otherwise ordinary situations to sustain a fairly stable, healthy level of emotional and physical health, in addition to the capacity for productive encounters and positive emotions, in the face of an isolated and potentially extremely disruptive event, such as the passing away of a close relative or an assault or life-threatening situation.

Walker, Pflingst, Carnevali, Sgoifo, and Nalivaiko: The capacity of an individual to endure and adjust to unfavorable and traumatic experiences is known as psychological resilience.

According to a review of the research by McMillen (1999), "people frequently believe that they gained insight from extremely challenging life experiences." This is important to notice across many studies and traumas.

According to Ungar's (2008) definition and concept of resilience, social context, familial dynamics, and individual characteristics all have a significant impact on resilience.

"Resilience refers to an ongoing process including beneficial adaptation within a setting of significant adversity," state Lothar, Cicchetti, and Becker (2000). When discussing the concept of resilience, Lothar and colleagues (2000) address two crucial circumstances: (a) being exposed to danger or adversity, and (b) succeeding in positive adaptation.

People with resilience have the mental fortitude to handle stress and adversity. It is mental strength that people may draw upon to get through difficult situations without crumbling. According to psychologists, resilient people are better equipped to deal with this kind of hardship and start again after a disaster.

Stress and challenges in life are not removed by resilience. Individuals with this kind of perseverance

don't have rose-colored glasses on. They understand that obstacles are unavoidable and that living can be challenging and unpleasant at times. They still experience the pain, grief, and sense of loss that come with a disaster, but they are able to move past these feelings and go on because of their attitude on life.

Resilience is correlated with the following traits:

- Having a good self-perception and self-efficacy.
- Being able to set and adhere to reasonable goals.
- Possessing an internal locus of control,
- Being an effective communicator and considering oneself as a combatant as opposed to a victim.
- Possessing strong emotional intelligence and adeptly controlling feelings.

Objectives

- To compare the rumination and stress among women and men.
- To compare the rumination and stress levels among different age groups.

Hypotheses

1. There is a significantly stronger correlation between rumination and stress among women than men.
2. There is a significantly stronger correlation between rumination and stress in youthful grownups (18-30 years) than in older grown-ups (31-45 years)

Method

Sample The sample for the study was comprised of 200 adults. 50 men and 50 women for the first age group (20-30 years) and 50 men and 50 women for the second age group (30-45 years).

Exclusion criteria: Those who have not reported some levels of stress are excluded from the research.

Inclusion criteria: Those who have reported some levels of stress are included in the research.

Procedure

Participants were requested to complete the set of self-questionnaire reports of stress after examining the stress levels in the individual self-report of another questionnaire for rumination is asked to complete. In this study following measures were used to examine the relation between rumination and stress in the individual.

Psychological measures

Stress scale.

One of the traditional tools for assessing stress is the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS). The instrument originated in 1983, but it's still commonly used to understand how distinct circumstances influence our feelings and how much pressure we experience. The Likert scale has five points: 0 for never, 1 for practically never, 2 for sporadically, 3 for quite regularly, and 4 for very frequently.

Rumination scale

The degree of rumination was determined by using the rumination reflection questionnaire (Trapnell, P. D., & Campbell, J. D., 1999). The 24-item scale uses a 5-point grading system to indicate how much you agree or disagree with each statement (1 being strongly

disagree, 2 disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree, and 5 strongly agree).

Resilience scale

The short-form CD-RISC developed by Campbell-Sills and Stein (2007) served as the model for the updated version. Scores on this brief unidimensional measure are substantially linked with ratings on the initially developed instrument; in fact, Campbell-Sills and Stein claim that the modified 10-item CD-RISC measure "captures the main features of resilience" (p. 1027). One extra CD-RISC item—know where to turn for help—that was absent from the Campbell-Sills and Stein modified assessment was included in this study. This item was allowed to include because the individual taking part was specifically asked to "think about how you as well as your spouse manage stressful situations or challenging times which arise in life," and the study was focused on a particular romantic relationship. It used a seven-point rating system (1 means it's seldom true, 7 that it's almost always true; $\alpha = .81$, $M = 5.52$, $SD = .72$).

Self-Concept Clarity Scale (SCC)

This self-report questionnaire contains 12 items that assess the stability, cohesiveness, and precision of one's beliefs (e.g., "my beliefs about myself often conflict with one another" (reverse scored) and "I seldom experience conflict between the different aspects of my personality") (Campbell et al., 1996). Participants rated each item on an extended Six-point Likert magnitude, which was constructed from the initial 5-point scale and varied between 1 (strongly agreeing) to Six (strongly disagreed).

Results

The intensity and direction of the relationship between rumination, resilience, and self-concept, and felt stress were ascertained by a multivariate correlational analysis.

Table 1: Intercorrelations between PSS, RQS, SCC, and RS Scores

	Measures	I	II	III	IV
I.	PSS	--			
II.	RSQ	.570**	--		
III.	SCC	-.237**	-.361**	--	
IV.	RS	-.378**	-.442**	.119	--

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < 0.01$ (2-tailed), Pearson Correlation is depicted in the table. Perceived Stress Scale indicates as PSS; Ruminative Response Style Questionnaire is indicates as RSQ; Self-concept Clarity Scale indicates as SCC; Resilience Scale is indicates as RS.

As shown in Table 1, there was a significant large positive correlation between perceived stress and rumination ($r = .58$, $n = 164$, $p < .01$, $r^2 = .34$), with higher levels of perceived stress associated with higher levels of rumination. When viewed by gender, a moderate to large significant correlation was found for

both males ($r = .46$, $n = 59$, $p < 0.01$, $r^2 = .21$; see Table 3) and females ($r = .60$, $n = 105$, $p < 0.01$, $r^2 = .36$; see Table 3), with females showing a slightly larger correlation between perceived stress and rumination. This result would suggest that women tend to ruminate more than men about their stressors as stress levels increase, but upon examining the group difference between correlation it was concluded that there was no statistically significant difference in the strength of the correlation between perceived stress and rumination for males and females.

Discussion

Rumination and stress are two correlated aspects of an individual who is experiencing stress in his/her life. College-going students usually face stressful situations in their life which affects their cognitive thoughts and behaviours. This study mainly focuses on the student's stress and rumination aspects which further reveals their self-concept and resilience. Results in the study reveal that females have a high correlation of stress with rumination, have a low level of self-concept and low resilience while males also have a high correlation of stress with rumination has low level of self-concept and low resilience. However, on comparing the data of females and males' correlation, females tend to have higher rumination levels with stress. Females are more likely to ruminate in a stressful situation than men. This can be more supported by the fact that females are more likely to be emotional or sensitive even a small disturbance or difference in their can cause them to think about their situation and what people will think while males on the other hand have a more convenient way to deal with the stressful situation and think practically about the situation not about the people which makes them more flexible to deal with many stressful situations.

On the comparison of older adults and young adults, it is revealed that rumination in stressful situations is high in young adults. As these people have less experience of life than older adults and have not seen much in life, while on the other hand, older adults tend to ruminate less in stressful situations as they have been struggling with life for many years and may have gone through it and now finds the solution of their stressful situation. These older adults also have higher resilience and a higher level of self-concept than young adults. These young adults are in those years in which they might have relationship issues, career issues, or are in their struggling phase from personal and professional aspects while the older adults have made their lives more stable life in terms of their personal and professional lives.

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